

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 20, No. 4

Dear Readers,

I am happy to announce the second regular issue of the year. In this issue we have 5 high quality papers from authors coming from five countries and three continents. I want to take the opportunity to gratefully thank all institutions and individuals - including the consortium members, members of the editorial board and the authors - for their support and effort to make J.UCS one of the high quality journals in computer science.

The authors Sana Ajmal, Asim Rasheed, Amir Qayyum and Aamir Hasan from Pakistan review connectivity issues in vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANET) with emphasis on routing, offer comprehensive literature review on state of the art in VANET routing, and compare some standard architectures. In a collaborative research between Serbia and Brazil, Darko Brodić, Carlos A. Mello, Čedomir A. Maluckov and Zoran N. Milivojević propose an approach to estimate the text skew for printed documents, and examine the performance by testing on a custom dataset. Ingrid Christensen, Silvia Schiaffino from Argentina discuss in their work a hybrid approach based on group profiling for homogeneous and non-homogenous groups by combining three familiar individual recommendation approaches: collaborative filtering, content-based filtering and demographic information. Patricia Matsumoto and Eduardo Guerra from Brazil introduce an approach for mapping domain-specific adaptive object model (AOM) applications to a general model and evaluate the approach by a case study. Finally, the authors Aad Slootmaker, Hub Kurvers, Hans Hummel and Rob Koper from The Netherlands report in their paper on the design, development and evaluation of the EMERGO platform for scenario-based serious games for complex cognitive skills acquisition.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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